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**Assessment of Supports and Challenges of Rural-Urban Migration among Irrigation Farmers in Kano
North Senatorial District, Kano State**

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Abstract

This study investigated assessment on supports and challenges of rural-urban migration among irrigation farmers in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State. Two research questions were formulated for the study. The design for this study was descriptive survey research. The population of the study was six thousand two hundred and eighty-seven (6,287) irrigation farmers in the study area, simple random sampling techniques were used to select the sample size of 361 respondents. Researcher developed questionnaire titled: Questionnaire on irrigation farming and reduction of rural-urban migration (QIFRRUM). The instrument for data collection was a 10 items questionnaire which was validated by research experts and tested with a reliability estimate of 0.68 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) (PPMC). The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The findings indicated among others that the support received by the irrigation farmers include water pump machines, pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, soil conditioners, and loan schemes; the challenges facing the irrigation farmers indicate inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines, inability to access loan schemes, and inefficient extension services. It was concluded therefore that supports received by irrigation farmers improved socio-economic condition, thereby providing a means of their livelihood generally in the areas of the study to determine rural-urban migration. It is recommended among others things that: government at all levels federal, state, and local non-governmental organizations and other philanthropist should be providing continuous support to irrigation farmers to mitigate rural-urban migration. Support in the area of water pump machines, pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, and loan schemes.

Keyword: Support, Challenges, Rural-Urban Migration

Introduction

The practice of rural development has been a global phenomenon as well as an age-long intervention effort by governments, non-governmental organizations and philanthropic foundations. Rural development generally denotes the processes leading to sustainable improvement in the quality of life of rural people especially the poor (Singh, 2002). In most developing countries of the world, rural areas occupy more geographical space than urban centers. This is why most rural locations are predominantly agriculture-based. In other words, majority of the people living in the rural areas of most developing nations are practicing subsistence agriculture (farming) as a way of sustaining their livelihood (Abbas, 2016).

In many developing nations, there had been a rapid growth of urban populations more than that of rural population (Andersen, 2013). In Africa, for instance, it has been estimated that between 1990 and 2020 there had been added at least 500 million people to the existing urban population compared to the less than 200 million people in North America and Europe (USAID, 2002). Such rapid urban growth in these African countries, including Nigeria, started even before independence. Nigeria is a typical example of this rapid urban growth, where there had been a tremendous expansion of urban areas, resulting in rapid urbanization at the expense of rural location and leading to rural-urban migration (Ledant, 2023).

However, the phenomenon of people migrating to other areas in search of a better life is not a novel one because the nexus of migration either rural-urban or urban-urban with development or otherwise is a subject of debate (Getso & Haruna, 2021). Therefore, rural-urban migration results from the search for perceived or recalled opportunities as a result of rural urban inequality in wealth. This inequality is as a result of the imbalance in the provision of social amenities for communities. Research findings, over the years, show an overwhelming concentration of wealth, assets, purchasing capacity, economic activities and a variety of services in urban centers as well as the continued neglect and degradation of rural areas (Chukwuedozie, Ajaero and Onokala, 2013). This assumption can be buttressed based on the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2014) report, which shows that the internal disparity between rural and urban areas was still very high in Nigeria. It is

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interesting to note that rural-urban migration in post-colonial Nigeria was equally practiced because Erringe (2012) reported that the record from 1963 indicated that 80.7% of the National population resided in rural areas. But the proportion dropped to 70.13% in 1985, and 69% in 1990, as noted by Moughalu (1992). The number of people residing in rural areas continued to decline; like in 2006 53% resided in rural areas and 51.6% in 2022.

Statement of the Research Problem:

Rural development is an interdisciplinary area of practice which aims at the improvement of the living conditions of rural dwellers. Rural development programmes are aimed at reducing poverty, providing jobs, improving income, imparting useful knowledge, attitude and skills and facilitating ultimate change among rural people. The phenomenon of rural-urban migration is an important feature of rural life that exposes rural youth to various hazards, inculcates dependency, breeds crimes and renders migrant families vulnerable to diseases, rape, hunger and insecurity.

The introduction of irrigation rural development programmes in the Kano North Senatorial District is intended to improve the livelihood and wellbeing of rural communities as well as serve as a means of reducing the trend of rural-urban migration prevailing in the area. In some Local Government Areas of the Kano North Senatorial District, such as Bagwai, Bichi, Danbatta, Dawakin Tofa, Gwarzo, Gabasawa, Kabo, Kunchi, Makoda, Rimin-Gado, Shanono, Tofa and Tsanyawa, irrigation agricultural activities are taking place and youth in the area are being employed in irrigation sites as laborers, marketers, transporters, seed multipliers, and so on. This seems to prevent them from migrating out because they have employment and business opportunities at home. However, these programmes and strategies implemented over the years impacted greatly on the reduction of rural-urban migration. Despite the significant research on a particular irrigation rural development there are may be a lack of understanding mechanism of irrigation rural development in reduction of rural-urban migration in Kano North, although much research has been done on irrigation rural development programmes, the exact mechanism that lead to the rural-urban migration are not yet fully understood and affects farmers to increased dependences on hired labour by rural households whose most productive members are lost to urban areas and courses labour shortage on large scale. This study therefore, intended to find out the supports received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration as well as challenges facing them in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of this study were to examine;

- i. The supports received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State;
- ii. The challenges facing irrigation farmers in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State;

Research Questions:

The following research questions guided this study:

- i. What is the support received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State?
- ii. What are the challenges facing irrigation farmers in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State?

Methodology

Descriptive Survey research design was adopted for the study. It is a design in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group (Akuezuilo, 2002).

The population for this study comprised the entire Irrigation Farmers from the 13 Local Governments areas in Kano North Senatorial District. According to available statistics there are six thousand two hundred and eighty seven 6,287 (KNARDA 2020 Records). The totals of 361 Irrigation Farmers were selected as respondents for the study out of the total of 6,287 that include irrigation farmers and executive members. The selection was based on the suggestions of the Krejcie and Morgan (2006) table for determining the sample size from a given population. A simple random sampling technique was adopted to select the relevant sample of 361 for the study. In applying the procedure, the researcher utilized two different sampling approaches to select the samples for the study in two phases; purposive sampling procedure and proportionate sampling procedure.

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The instruments of data collection were self-developed instruments titled Questionnaire on irrigation farming and reduction of rural-urban migration (QIFRRUM) by the researcher. The instrument has two sections A and B. Section A has respondent's demographic information while section B had 10 items on the research questions, in the form of modified 4-point likert scale. The answering pattern provided multiple options for the respondents to choose, as Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD), the questionnaires were scored on the scale of SA= 4, A= 3, D= 2 and SD= 1. Therefore, the decision rule is based on the scale that a mean of 2.50 and above is considered as Agreed and a mean of below 2.50 as Disagreed was designed to elicit information from the respondents to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with the items. The instrument was validated by experts. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, the test-re-test method was used. The results obtained were correlated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) (PPMC) and the reliability coefficient of 0.68 obtained showed the instrument is reliable for use in this study.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the support received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State?

This research question was answered using frequency and percentages (%). Also, the average mean and standard deviation is presented in the following Table where N=361:

Table 4.1 Supports Received by Irrigation Farmers in Kano North Senatorial District.

Variables	SA F (%)	A F (%)	D F (%)	SD F (%)	Mean	SD	Decision
Water pump machines and pipe connector fitting	164 (45.4%)	183 (50.7%)	14 (3.9%)	-	3.42 +3	0.566	Agree
Fertilizers	23 (6.4%)	225 (62.3%)	113 (31.3%)	-	3.25	0.561	Agree
Agro-chemicals; liming, acidifying agent and soil conditioners	108 (29.9%)	251 (69.5%)	2 (0.6%)	-	3.29	0.468	Agree
Provision of canal by government	121 (33.5%)	217 (60.1%)	23 (6.4%)	-	3.27	0.571	Agree
Provision of tractors for harrowing on free charge	-	-	198 (54.8%)	163 (45.2%)	1.55	0.498	Disagree
Seminars on strategies of irrigation farming systems	208 (57.6%)	153 (42.4%)	-	-	3.42	0.495	Agree
Providing of adequate water to irrigation farmers associations	140 (38.8%)	185 (51.2%)	36 (10%)	-	3.29	0.637	Agree
Provisions of store or aggregation centers to irrigation farmers Associations	126 (34.9%)	181 (50.1%)	44 (12.2%)	10 (2.8%)	3.17	0.744	Agree
Provisions of loan scheme to irrigation farmers	180 (49.9%)	179 (49.6%)	2 (0.6%)	-	3.49	0.512	Agree
Provisions of efficient management to irrigation farmers	145 (40.2%)	207 (57.3%)	9 (2.5%)	-	3.38	0.534	Agree

Field Survey, 2023

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The results presented in Table 4.5 indicate ten variables as the support received by irrigation farmers towards the reduction of rural-urban migration in Kano North Senatorial District. All the ten (10) supports received by irrigation farmers presented to the respondents were responded to by the 361 samples. Thus, nine out of the ten items were agreed as the support received by irrigation farmers. An individual assessment of the supports received by the irrigation farmers shows that in Item 1, the highest frequency of 183 (50.7%) agreed that water pump machines and pipe connector fittings are some of the support with a mean score of 3.42 (SD=0.566). In Item 2, the highest frequency of 225(62.3%) agreed that fertilizers are some of the supports with a mean of 3.25(SD=0.561). In Item 3, the highest frequency of 251(69.5%) agreed that agro-chemicals, liming, acidifying agents and soil conditioners with a mean of 3.29 (SD=0.468). In Item 4, the highest frequency of 217(60.1%) agreed with the provision of canal by government with a mean of 3.27(SD=0.571). in Item 5, the highest frequency of 198 (54.8%) disagreed that the provision of tractors for harrowing on free charge. However, in Item 6, the highest frequency of 208 (57.6%) strongly agreed on the seminars on the strategies of irrigation farming systems (Mean=3.42, SD=0.495). In Item 7, the highest frequency of 185 (51.2%) agreed on providing adequate water to irrigation farmer associations with a mean of 3.29 (SD=0.637). In Item 8, the highest frequency of 181 (50.1%) agreed on the provisions of stores or aggregation centers to irrigation farmer Associations with a mean of 3.17(SD=0.744). In Item 9, the highest frequency of 180 (49.9%) strongly agreed on the provisions of loan scheme to irrigation farmers with a mean of 3.49(SD=0.512). In Item 10, the highest frequency of 207 (57.3%) agreed on the provisions of efficient management to irrigation farmers with a mean of 3.38(SD=0.534). Overall, the participants agreed that nine out of the ten (10) statements were the supports received by irrigation farmers for the reduction of rural-urban migration because all the nine-item mean scores are above the decision rule of 2.5.

Research Question 2: What are the challenges facing irrigation farmer’s in Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State?

This research question was answered using frequency and percentages (%). Also, the average mean and standard deviation is presented in the following Table where N=361:

Table 4.2: Challenges Facing Irrigation Farmers

Variables	SA F (%)	A F (%)	D F (%)	SD F (%)	Mean	SD	Decision
Inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines	104 (28.8%)	243 (67.3%)	14 (3.9%)	-	3.25	0.515	Agree
Access to loan scheme to irrigation farmers	120 (33.2%)	223 (61.8%)	18 (5%)	-	3.28	0.551	Agree
Inadequate technical advice to irrigation farmers	108 (29.9%)	245 (67.9%)	8 (2.2%)	-	3.28	0.495	Agree
Inefficient extension services	129 (35.7%)	202 (56%)	30 (8.3%)	-	3.27	0.605	Agree
Communication and adequate capacity building	153 (42.4%)	193 (53.5%)	13 (3.6%)	2 (0.6%)	3.38	0.584	Agree
Startup capital and irregular fuel supply	147 (40.7%)	208 (57.6%)	-	6 (1.7%)	3.37	0.579	Agree
Poor quality of local manufacturing and frequent breakdown	135 (37.4%)	187 (51.8%)	39 (10.8%)	-	3.27	0.642	Agree
Poor direction and clear strategy on irrigation farming	136 (37.7%)	175 (48.5%)	40 (11.1%)	10 (2.8%)	3.21	0.745	Agree
Poor effective monitoring of irrigation activities	183 (50.7%)	178 (49.3%)	-	-	3.51	0.501	Agree
High costs of inputs	146 (40.4%)	206 (57.1%)	9 (2.5%)	-	3.38	0.535	Agree

Field Survey, 2023

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The results presented in Table 4.7 indicate ten variables as the challenges facing irrigation farmers in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State. All the ten (10) challenges presented to the respondents were responded to by the 361 samples. Thus, all the ten items were agreed as the challenges facing the irrigation farmers. An individual assessment of the challenges indicated that in Item 1, the highest frequency of 243 (67.3%) agree that inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines is one of the challenges with a mean of 3.25 (SD=0.515). In Item 2, the highest frequency of 223 (61.8%) agreed about the inability to access loan schemes to irrigation farmers with a mean of 3.28 (SD=0.551). In Item 3, the highest frequency of 245(67.9%) agreed on inadequate technical advice to irrigation farmers with a mean of 3.28 (SD=0.495). In Item 4, the highest frequency of 202 (56%) agreed on inefficient extension services with a mean of 3.27 (SD=0.605). In Item 5, the highest frequency of 193 (53.5%) agreed on communication and adequate capacity building with a mean of 3.38 (SD=0.584). In Item 6, the highest frequency of 208 (57.6%) agreed on startup capital and irregular fuel supply with a mean of 3.37 (SD=0.579). In Item 7, the highest frequency of 187 (51.8%) agreed on poor quality of local manufacturing and frequent breakdown with a mean of 3.27 (SD=0.642). In Item 8, the highest frequency of 175 (48.5%) agreed on poor direction and clear strategy on irrigation farming with a mean of 3.21 (SD=0.745). In Item 9, the highest frequency of 183 (50.7%) strongly agreed on poor effective monitoring of irrigation activities with a mean of 3.51(SD=0.501). Lastly, in Item 10, the highest frequency of 206 (57.1%) agreed on high costs of inputs with a mean of 3.38 (SD=0.535). Overall, the participants agreed that all the ten (10) statements were the challenges facing irrigation farmers in the Kano North Senatorial District because all the mean score were above the decision rule of 2.5.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding revealed that the supports received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State are water pump machines, pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, agro-chemicals, liming and acidifying agent and soil conditioners, seminars on the strategies of irrigation farming systems and the provisions of stores, and of loan schemes. Accordingly, this finding is also inline and complements the respondents responses with the various irrigation farmers' leaders from others areas, towards improving irrigation rural development among community members as well as encouragement with a view to determine rural-urban migration among the rural communities in the study areas. The farmers highlighted the various supports received from Kano state government from 2016 to date as part of its effort under the Commercial Agricultural Credit Scheme (CACCS), disbursed N1 billion interest-free loans to over 4,000 members of 517 associations of irrigation farmers in the state to revitalize agriculture, empower farmers and ensure food security in the state and the country at large, (Premium Times, 2016). The state government also supported various irrigation farmer associations with water pump machines and pipe connector fitting, the provision of canals, fertilizers, agro-chemical, tractors for harrowing on free loan, seminars on the strategies of irrigation system, providing aggregation centers, loan schemes to irrigation farmers and also of experiences to efficient management of irrigation farmers in order improve productivity towards irrigational rural development programmes. This is said to be an initiative out of the need to re-invent agriculture in the state, which is the key solution to the current economic recession and an opportunity for farmers to boost their productivity, income and standard of living. Awe (2013) examined the mobilization of domestic financial resources for agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Some of the financial resources the study identified included credit facilities from the Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industries (NBCI) and credit provided by commercial and merchant banks. The results revealed that these facilities have a positive relationship with agricultural productivity. Anyebe & Ikani (2015) who assessed agricultural credit on rural farmers in Nigeria through the administration of questionnaires found that credits to agriculture had sufficiently boosted productivity in the sector. The work is related to this research in the sense that the former explains how locally generated sources of finance affects productivity positively. However, Bhattacharya and Narayan (2015) showed the impact of formal credit in India, which is usually provided at subsidized interest rates. They found that formal credit increased income and agric-productivity and calculated that benefits exceeded the cost by at least 13 percent, using district level panel data. The work investigated how increased farmer income and productivity are subjected to subsidized-rate credits. Meaning, when loan is subsidized, there is every tendency for it to improve income and output. Therefore, if this is held as a trend, the marginal propensity of income and output will be much higher when the rate is declared zero or free. This is what this research intends to explore. Diagne and Zeller (2001) found in Malawi that rural banks, savings and cooperative society's priority in issuing loans to households with diversified asset portfolios and diversified incomes. Households do not consider interest rates an important factor while deciding to choose financial institution. Non-price attributes such as types of loan provided and restriction on their use as well

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as the non-financial services provided play an important role. The work discusses factors that qualify individuals for loan, which is very essential while designing a repayment mechanism. The irrigation farmers leaders revealed that in terms of loan many things attributed to a long delay in disbursement to irrigation farmers in the rural areas. Since most of the banks are located in cities, in some cases where a loan is approved, it arrives too late for it to fulfill the purpose for which it was intended. Moreover, this is also supported with by the work of Akinleye, Akanni Oladoja (2005), who wrote on the appraisal of the agricultural credit guarantee scheme in Nigeria. They also found that the scheme failed in bringing about the desired productivity of the agricultural sector. Ike (2007) conducted his study on institutional loan recovery in Nigeria. He classified the problems of loan recovery into three: farmer related problems; structural problems and bank related problems. It was found out that even though there was a positive relationship between agricultural support and output, yet a significant percentage of farmers was illiterate, ignorant and misinterpret the objectives of the government in granting agricultural loans. Hence, loans were diverted to non-agricultural purposes and sometimes used for traditional ceremonies. This is also indicated that some farmers could not manage their projects due to over expansion, natural hazards and loan mismanagement. Structural problems relate to security, like supply and demand for funds and the interest rate structure. Loans are usually made against security for agricultural production. Most farmers do not have tangible security. They may have guarantors but the main disadvantage of pledging them as security is that in case of non-repayment; they may disappear, thereby failing to fulfill their loan obligations. The farmers highlighted some of the bank related problems to include: lending policies and procedures as well as the personnel capacity of the banks; some bank managers do not apply the principles of good lending while giving loans to farmers and, lastly, the problem of skilled and an adequate number of bank staff to formalize loans as well as the follow up process. The work has a relationship with this work, because it investigated the problems of loan recovery in Nigeria, which is also one of these research objectives. However, this research extended or further investigated the negative role interest rate play to the detriment of loan repayment in the study area. Moreover, issues relating to farmers' illiteracy vis-à-vis loan mismanagement will all be given special priority in order to expose them to the Islamic agricultural source of finance. This is consistent with the finding of Kareem (2013) who revealed that foreign direct investment: commercial bank loan, interest rate and food import value, had a positive relationship with agricultural output. This finding is inconsistent with Adetiloye (2012) on agricultural financing in Nigeria in that credit to the agricultural sector is significant but noted that credit supply had not been growing in relation to the economy. The finding also agreed with that of Tasie Offor (2013) about government providing support to rural farmers as credit supply in River state, Nigeria and that the credit programme had contributed significantly to farm output and income. In the same vein, Chisasa Makina (2015) opined that although credit was not well provided to rural farmers, credit supply had a positive and significant impact on agricultural output in the long run. This finding further confirms the recent development by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) that introduced Anchor Borrowers' Program (ABP). The Program which was launched by President Muhammad Buhari (GCFR) on November 17, 2015 was intended to create a linkage between anchor companies involved in the processing and small holder farmers (SHFs) of the required key agricultural commodities. The program thrust of the ABP is the provision of farm inputs in kind and cash (for farm labor) to small holder farmers to boost the production of these commodities, stabilize inputs supply to agro-processors and address the country's negative balance of payments on food. At harvest, the SHF supplies his/her produce to the Agro-processor (Anchor) who pays the cash equivalent to the farmer's account. The loan shall be targeted at smallholder farmers engaged in the production of identified commodities across the country.

The second finding of this study indicates that, the challenges facing irrigation farmers in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State and shows that the inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines, in-ability to access loan scheme to irrigation farmers, inadequate technical advice to irrigation farmers, inefficient extension services, communication and adequate capacity building, startup capital and irregular fuel supply, poor quality of local manufacturing and frequent breakdown, poor direction and clear strategy on irrigation farming, poor effective monitoring of irrigation activities and high costs of inputs were the challenges. The implication of this is that through appropriate rural development programme by government, rural-urban migration can be curtailed, thereby making rural inhabitants economically self-reliant through irrigation rural development infrastructures. The findings also revealed that Government needs to do more to stem rural-urban migration. Government must intensify rural development in Nigeria as expected by majority of the rural populace. People in rural areas have no need to migrate to urban centers if basic social amenities and other variables to make them comfortable are provided. This finding is consistent with that of Oravee (2015), who reported that the challenges of inadequate funding of the river basins could be traced

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back to 1989, which was instrumental to discontinuing of direct involvement in farming activities by some of the River Basins and Rural Development Authorities consequently leading to the in-effectiveness of the scheme.

The attitudes and interests of the participating farmers have a larger role to play when it comes to Nigeria's irrigation farming. The government and its agencies in charge of irrigation systems need to be proactive in discharging their duties and correspondingly provide a platform to encourage and sensitize farmers on the need to engage in irrigation farming rather than on only the rain-fed. In addition, farmers are not interested in the operation and maintenance of the large-scale irrigation facilities. Furthermore, the irrigation farmers leaders revealed that the major constraints in utilizing irrigation potential through large-scale schemes include: Unwieldy functions of the RBDAs resulting in dilution of their functions relating to efficient management of irrigation projects, Scarcity of experienced, dedicated, motivated and technically sound manpower ready to implement the project on a sustainable basis, results in sub-optimal managed projects, Lack of direction and clear strategy on the development of irrigation by the government, Shortage, and at times the delayed release of finances by the government, Unwillingness of small farmers (less-powerfulness) to participate in the scheme as they continue to doubt the reliability and timeliness of irrigation water to them at their tail-end plots, lack of enough fertilizers, engines and agro-chemicals, Inadequate technical advice to irrigation farmers, lack of direction and clear strategy on irrigation farming, canal erosion and land degradation in the field, lack of adequate startup capital and irregular fuel supply, lack of effective monitoring and improper maintenance. These farmers are expected to constitute the bulk of the beneficiaries.

Similarly, Adekunle (2015) found out that poor knowledge of irrigation techniques among farmers was one of the factors affecting their participation enlarge-scale irrigation scheme. Those that manage to participate are not equipped with the requisite knowledge for the operations and maintenance of facilities. This problem is one of the current challenges being faced by the large-scale irrigation scheme in Nigeria. Population in cities and sub-urban areas in developing countries, including Nigeria, is expected to increase from 1.9 billion in 2000 to 3.9 billion in 2030. This is principally attributed to rural to urban migration, which is consequent upon dichotomous planning and development many developing countries adopted. This subsequently results in the rural deprived and the urban endowed that translates into improved amenities and economic opportunities in urban centres than rural areas (Abdullahi, Shaibu-Imodagbe, Mohammed, Sa'id & Idris, 2015).

Conclusion

The study revealed the support received by irrigation farmers towards reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State are water pump machines, pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, agro-chemicals, liming and acidifying agent and soil conditioners, seminars on the strategies of irrigation farming systems and the provisions of stores, and of loan schemes. Therefore, the supports received by irrigation farmers improved socio-economic condition, thereby providing a means of their livelihood generally in the areas of the study to determine rural-urban migration that is already present and includes access to increased employment opportunity of rural dwellers, boosting income levels, irrigation farming reduces the level of poverty among the rural dwellers, improves their food security of the rural dwellers, improves their general living conditions and also promotes self-reliance and independence among the community members. The result also from the data analyses revealed that irrigation rural development has immensely contributed to the reduction of rural-urban migration in the Kano North Senatorial District.

Similarly, the findings on the challenges revealed that, inadequacy of fertilizers and water pump machines, inability to access loan schemes, inadequate technical advice, inefficient extension services, communication and adequate capacity building and high cost of inputs. Thus, it can be concluded that despite the above challenges, irrigational rural development programmes enhance communities members to improve their skills, socio-economic status and employment opportunities thereby reduction rural-urban migration in order to stay in their communities.

Recommendations

- i. Government at all levels (Federal, State, and Local) Non-governmental organizations and other philanthropist should be providing continuous support to irrigation farmers to mitigate rural-urban migration. Support in the area of water pump machines and pipe connector fitting, fertilizers, agro-chemicals; liming, acidifying agents and soil conditioners, the provision of canal by government, seminars on the strategies of irrigation farming systems, providing adequate water,

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store or aggregation centers, loan schemes, efficient management, is needed by irrigation farmers for the reduction of rural-urban migration.

- ii. Kano State Government should intensify efforts in the provision of adequate fertilizers and water pump machines, access to loan schemes to irrigation farmers, adequate technical advice and the provision of efficient extension services, communication and adequate capacity building in order to determine the challenges facing irrigation farmers in the Kano North Senatorial District, Kano State Nigeria.

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